

Becoming a Synodal Pastoral Leader

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Abstract

Pope Francis wants ‘Synodality’ as a principle and practice in the everyday life of the local Churches or ‘*synodalization*’ of the entire Church and ‘*institutionalization*’ of listening and dialogue. Hence, the leader in the ‘Synodal church’ should be one, who can plant dreams, allow hope to flourish, inspire trust, weave together relationships, and learn from one another. He is “there with the people” as an enabling and empowering presence. He has to be visionary, inspiring, enlightened, and creative, and possess a participatory mindset, ecclesial sense, capacity for meaningful delegation. This calls for a paradigm shift from the old authority-based governance (*authoritarianism/clericalism*) to one of “enabling and empowering pastoral power.” In this way, ‘synodality will become a threshold for the Church to cross for its life and its mission,’ and will lead to the emergence of the Church as a communion of communities, creating space for the Spirit and one another, and forging ahead with a sense common mission.

Introduction

The Sixteenth Ordinary Assembly of the Synod of Bishops on the theme “For a Synodal Church: Communion, Participation, and Mission” is to take place in two sessions in 2023 (4-29 October) and in 2024. The Synod of Bishops is one of the ‘decentralizing’ institutions resulting from the Second Vatican Council as an important means to put into practice collegiality by which the bishops of the Catholic Church with its head, bear responsibility for its life, mission, and governance. This was done to balance the excessively centralized role of the Pope, to give concrete expression to the principle of collegiality and to make it an enduring practice. Nevertheless, the Synods remained at a higher level of

deliberation *by selected bishops*. Now, Pope Francis wants to make it a principle and practice in the everyday life of the local Churches

Pope Francis has clear ideas about the Synod on Synodality: “to plant dreams, draw forth prophecies and visions, allow hope to flourish, inspire trust, bind up wounds, weave together relationships, awaken a dawn of hope, learn from another and create a bright resoluteness that will enlighten minds, warm hearts, give strength to our hands...” (*Preparatory Document*, PD, 32).

Synodality in the Church

Synodality means the path along which the People of God walk together. The image of people walking along a path together evokes an image of friends sharing words of wisdom and caring for one another along the journey. It is a method and process of discussion and participation in which the whole people of God can listen to the Holy Spirit and to one another, and take part in the life and mission of the Church.

Since the synodal structure is ‘constitutive of the Church,’ Pope Francis wants a Church that is more and more ‘synodal’ both by way of being and by way of functioning. The Synod Preparatory Document states: “Ultimately, this path of walking together is the most effective way of manifesting and putting into practice the nature of the Church as the pilgrim and missionary People of God” (PD, 1). Hence, the objective of the synodal process is not to provide a temporary or occasional or one-time experience of synodality, but rather to provide an opportunity for the entire People of God to discern together, how to become a more synodal Church in the long-term or rather, ‘synodalization’ of the entire Church, and ‘institutionalization’ of listening, dialogue, and discernment. Pope Francis wants to place the entire Church in a condition to live an authentic synodal experience. We are re-learning synodality, and one of the main challenges is that, with synodality, we learn by doing.

Synodality in Practice in the Local Church

The Diocese is the Local Church. The Local Ordinary is one who takes care of the ‘household (of God).’ This pastoral responsibility is then extended to the pastors in the parishes. Originally the terms for diocese and ‘parish’ (*oikein/oikos*) meant living or dwelling together. The Pastoral leaders are to dwell together with the people or to be-there-with them in their midst. The essential features of the Church and meaningful actualization of synodality can be realized very concretely and most effectively in the local church, namely, community and communion, participation, and mission. This is because there is

better and continual interaction and personal ‘encounters’ at various levels, deeper solidarity, common interests, and concerns, and shared aspirations and goals.

The logo of the synod summarizes not only the synodal process but also the nature of the Church. The figures of the logo represent the entire humanity, journeying, listening to, sharing, and caring. The small child leading the group represents the ‘least’ and the ‘last.’ The people are moving forward towards a goal – a journeying dynamic Church, as against a status quo maintaining Church. The leader is “there-with them / in their midst” as a caring, enabling, and empowering presence.

The Role of Visionary, Inspiring, Enlightened, and Creative Leadership

The leaders of the ‘Synodal Church must be able “to plant dreams, draw forth prophecies and visions, and allow hope to flourish...” (PD, 32). Ages ago the wise man said, “Where there is no vision people perish” (Prov 29:18). The Church and society need leaders who are visionaries to give them direction and guidance for a goal in life. Rather than following one’s own fixed ways or becoming blind imitations, there is a need to think creatively, identify new needs, devise new methods and strategies, and set definite goals through systematic planning, and decisive action.

The leaders today have to devise ways and systems for sharing responsibility with other members of the pastoral team. This requires the leaders an inclusive approach to involve all sections of the people. This would also mean that the leaders realize that “authority is a sacred trust given by God to be used to empower others,” and nurture and foster the ministerial gifts of their collaborators, and the community as a whole.

Some leaders may tend to mistake good administration for inspiring and effective leadership - empowering model. As a result, they exercise a culture of control and are lost in routines and trifles – the transmission model. Management executes the agenda that the leader sets. The manager can only add, while the leader alone can multiply. When leadership is weak, effectiveness by multiplication suffers, and mediocrity creeps in.

Leadership today has a triple function: informative (enlightening communication), performative (challenging/motivating to action), and transformative (inviting to change). In other words, the leaders should be able to provide a vision to the community and society; they nurture people’s faith and sustain their hope.

The people expect from priests, especially in today's confused situation, intellectual leadership that is both challenging and stimulating, not just emotional responses, and stereotyped answers. While it is important to be on people's 'wavelength,' it is equally necessary to offer uplifting thoughts, critical, yet objective assessment of facts and events, constructive ideas, and a Christian perspective to questions and problems. This is particularly true about engaging the educated for serious discussions on important issues.

The moral and spiritual ascendancy of the leaders is of utmost importance. Pope Francis is seen and recognized as "the most powerful voice on earth for those not being heard." The Late Mr. Mikhail Gorbachev introduced St. Pope John Paul II to his wife (Raisa) as "the greatest moral authority on earth." It is a rare compliment from a communist about "the strongest anti-communist" of their times.

The Mission in the Church is Participatory

Participation is of paramount importance since without it both communion and mission cannot be effectively actualized. A viable model of a participatory Church for greater involvement of the laity is the 'Small Christian Community.' This can be very effective to facilitate the building up of communities of faith, characterized by communion, participation, and mission. This is a very relevant model for areas (e.g. tribal societies) where all the members of the community are involved in every aspect of its life.

The emerging understanding of ministry as a partnership in mission demands of the leaders greater involvement and co-responsibility, the spirit of dialogue, and above all, a participatory mindset. The rich and diverse human, spiritual and intellectual resources of all sections of the people of God can be of great assistance. In this way, leadership takes the form of empowerment of the community.

Strong Sense of 'Togetherness' or Belongingness

One basic requirement to ensure full collaboration is developing a strong sense of belongingness to Christ and to his Church and a feeling that we belong to each other. There should be a greater experience of 'communion' in the sense of 'togetherness,' beyond formalities of 'agreements,' and include informal interaction and pastorally fruitful relationships and interactions at various levels. Respectful attention to others, readiness to learn from others, and sharing of resources are both means for and fruit of this togetherness. Persons are the greatest asset for building up communion in the Church. All who are engaged

in building up the Body of Christ are co-workers of God and fellow workers among themselves (cf. 1 Cor 3:9). The fact that the building grows into a Temple of the Holy Spirit makes ministry in the Church ‘a sacred task’ (cf. 1 Cor 3:10-17; Eph 2:19-21), which should inspire us to an enhanced sense of responsibility and creative initiatives.

A strong ecclesial sense will prevent us from the unhealthy competition. Competitive superiority, be it individual or collective (the great threat of ‘spiritual worldliness’), should give way to collaborative excellence. Our concern will then be, how to bring enhanced quality to ministry and qualitative change to the lives of people.

Importance of Functioning within a ‘System’

The pastoral structures and administrative guidelines in the Church are meant to express the true spirit of synodality. Further, they promote the true spirit of communion through meaningful interaction, a greater sense of unity, better coordination and collaboration; they also demonstrate the fundamental equality of all believers, ensure active participation at all levels, and above all give a united witness to the Gospel.

Various canonical bodies/pastoral structures may have been set up: Council of Consultors, Presbyteral Council, Pastoral Council, Finance Committee, Managing Committee, Pastoral Commissions, etc. But it is good to carefully assess the quality of participation, especially the listening and common discernment taking place in these bodies. Some of the reasons for failure may be summed up as unwillingness to change the mindset, ‘clericalism’ in different forms,¹ absence of ‘ecclesial sense,’ lack of determination, with corresponding attitudes and behaviour patterns.

The pastoral structures and systems may not by themselves solve all problems, but if they are properly animated and made functional, the whole

¹Though the expression was originally applied only to ‘clerics,’ it now refers to a set of attitudes, diverse manifestations and a way of authoritarian behaviour resulting in gross abuse of power and position. Regarding ‘clericalism’ Pope Francis says: “The whole Church is called to deal with the weight of a culture imbued with clericalism and its forms of exercising authority on which the different types of abuse (power, economic, conscience, sexual) are grafted. Clericalism, which is “a terrible evil forgets that the visibility and sacramentality of the Church belong to all the faithful people of God...Let us be on guard, please, against this temptation. *To say ‘no’ to abuse is to say an emphatic ‘no’ to all forms of clericalism.*”

Church can become energetic and vibrant. This is clearly visible wherever functioning systems are followed. Going beyond mere formality, all should develop a strong sense of commitment and dedication to the common cause/good.

The awareness that the leaders are only stewards of the goods of the Church to be administered for common good (cf. Acts 4:32,34-35), should make them administer the resources judiciously, justly, and responsibly. The resources of the Church form ‘a sacred trust.’ Greater accountability, transparency, and shared responsibility can make stewardship more effective, ensure credibility and inspire confidence and trust in the people.

Listening and Discernment

Two frequently used terms in the Preparatory Document, are listening and discernment which constitutes the synodal process in its bipolarity: the vertical and horizontal.

Listening with a Heart: While hearing refers to the sphere of information, listening refers to the sphere of communication and requires closeness, engagement with the other, silence, and stillness. *The* “heart of the synodal experience is listening to God through listening to one another” (*Vademecum*, 4.1). Pope Francis wants leaders to develop the quality of listening as Jesus did. First, listen to the Spirit in silence and prayer, but without monopolizing or manipulating the Spirit. He invites all to listen with humility, speak freely and respectfully and speak the truth with boldness (*parrhesia*) and in charity (PD, 30/III; *Vademecum*, 4.1-2; 5.2.3.). The second aspect is listening to one another with the ‘heart.’ It has to be a mutual listening in which everyone has something to learn. He says that the Synodal process itself has to start by listening to the people, and especially to the dissenting voices, to those who feel sidelined, wounded, and to women, including religious women. Women Religious should not be considered as a mere workforce, but as equal partners in the mission of the Church. An atmosphere of trust and openness without stifling dissenting voices is essential.

Discernment: The synodal process of listening is oriented to discernment (*Vademecum*, 2.2). In this process, the real experiences of the people and the challenges they face should receive great attention. In a secular democracy, decisions are made going by the majority, which need not always be right! Pope Francis warns against the pragmatism of numbers and using majority as the definitive criterion for discernment. Persons cannot be “numbered” and reduced

to numbers. The ‘numbers-based approach,’ which he calls a “*space for hidden idolatry,*” depersonalizes’ the synodal process and tries to replace the person of the Holy Spirit. Instead, we must learn to step back in order to leave room for the Spirit. The other two spaces for hidden idolatry are ‘spiritual worldliness and functionalism.’

True discernment happens when the members have the common good of the community as their goal and not selfish motives and interests. The phenomenon of personal agenda and self-centredness replacing the common good can also be present in the Church. Synod is not about debate or discussion, rather, it is an exercise in ‘spiritual discernment or common apostolic discernment.’ As *Evangelii Gaudium* states it means to re-examine even some of the “beautiful” customs and practices (43) and one’s own favourite plans in view of surrendering to God’s will. St. Joseph and Our Mother Mary stand out as examples of listening with the heart and decision-making through a process of discernment, as they went through difficult situations and challenges.

Meaningful Delegation and De-centralization

Jesus chose the twelve and others, and empowered them to carry forward his movement (cf. Mk 3:13-19; Lk 10:1-12). The early Church too followed this process, as shown by the choice of deacons (cf. Acts 6:1-6). The result was that the ‘Word’ increased and the numbers ‘multiplied’ (cf. Acts 6:7). More than lessening the workload and increasing efficiency, meaningful delegation and de-centralization build up relationships and promote trust, confidence and a sense of belonging and inclusiveness among the co-workers. It brings out the servant model of leadership; it liberates the leaders from accusations of misuse of power or its overconcentration.

The delegation of power requires learning to remain in the background. St. Joseph is a typical example – remaining as he did in the shadow of Jesus and Mary. Most of the time, he is known as, and called, the ‘husband of Mary,’ while in his patriarchal tradition, it should have been the other way around! Without being in the limelight, he quietly played his crucial role in the history of salvation, often as the ‘second fiddle.’ The synodal path requires of leaders *a kind of spirituality of ‘hiddenness’ or ‘invisibility.’* Whatever is accomplished is the achievement of the co-workers and the community as a whole. This can be a great message to the world of orchestrated media publicity. Pastors are often called to do just ‘ordinary or routine’ works but in an extraordinary way. This calls for *deep interiority, self-assuredness, freedom from threat perception,* etc.

Leaders as an ‘Enabling’ Presence

The Evangelist Luke presents a very powerful image of journeying together (cf. 24:13-35). Here, Jesus brings hope, meaning, and a positive perspective on the future to the downcast disciples, who were running away from the centre of their lives. They shared their anxieties with the ‘stranger’ (Jesus). The stranger was willing to listen to them and to the stories about their shattered dreams. As they listened to him, they slowly came to the understanding that there is a path to their dilemma, and began to see a new light in the midst of distrust, loss, and darkness. They then invited him: “Stay with us.” Their moments of despair were transformed and empowered. He celebrated with them - the breaking of the bread/the Eucharist (communion). He took initiative to include them (participation). Finally, he empowered them to announce the Good News (mission). This process needs to be re-enacted in the process of synodality.

To pastor effectively demands that we move forward from ‘doing to enabling.’ There is a feeling that leaders have become more ‘administrators, managers and beneficiaries of a system’ than prophetic voices. There is also the opposition between the modern ‘urban’ approach and the ‘rural’ approach. The mission of the Church today is to be an ‘enabling’ and ‘empowering presence’ to those who are under different forms of marginalization and to help them re-discover their identity, and provide them with the right motivation, purpose, and perspective for life. But it can be done only by relying on God who is the transcendent source of life. This is where contemplation comes into its own and gives the correct orientation.

Learning from Cultures and Traditions of the People

Israel’s legislative measure had been inspired in a limited way by the surrounding cultures. The ethos of tribal/primal societies and values like equality, egalitarianism, fellowship, the attitude of sharing, etc., find their echo in the teaching of Jesus. Practices like community decision-making by striving for consensus rather than ‘majority,’ owning up responsibility for implementation, and accountability are strongly advocated in the ‘synodal way.’ These practices, based on tribal / clan loyalty, can serve as starting point in evolving an inculturated system and the Church can help to integrate them into the larger new ‘clan’(community) in loyalty to Christ and his Church. The Church systems then will better resonate with the actual practices of the people and become more relevant and effective, and avoid the danger of imposition of extraneous structures.

Change of Mindset

Some think that the greatest challenge for making the Church more ‘synodal,’ or making the synodal path a lived reality, both at personal and administrative levels, will be to get the priests on board, and to initiate a paradigm shift from ‘clericalism’ to the participatory mission, from power to service. Hence, the whole Church is called to deal with the weight of a culture imbued with clericalism. Pope Francis states: “Clericalism (which is “a terrible evil”) forgets that the visibility and sacramentality of the Church belong to all the faithful people of God...Let us be on guard, please, against this temptation.” The change of mindset may require a kind of ‘de-schooling’ (to discard some of the ‘inherited’ pyramidal images and ‘clerical’ attitudes) and ‘re-schooling’ (to imbibe a new mindset and values).

Empowering the Laity

The lay leaders have had an irreplaceable role in the story of the growth of the Church in NE India. The Apostolic Constitution, *‘Praedicate Evangelium’* (of Pope Francis) states: “Each Christian, by virtue of Baptism is a missionary disciple...This should consequently make provision for the involvement of lay women and men, also in roles of government and responsibility” (no I.10; cf. EG, 120). Authority in the Church has to enable the ministerial gifts of the laity to emerge and make them feel that they are responsible members of the Church (cf. LG 30; Eph 4:15-16). Hence, Vatican II insisted that all authority is to “promote the good of the faithful” (PO, 9), and to lead them “in dignity and freedom” towards their final destiny (LG, 18).

There are many areas of ministry particularly suited to their life and competence. But it is necessary that the laity receive adequate theological, spiritual, and pastoral formation to assume responsibilities in the Church (cf. LG, 32; EA, 32). Hence, systematic training and ongoing formation of the laity must become a regular feature at the parish, at diocesan and regional levels. The feasibility of establishing ‘lay ministries’ needs to be studied.²

²New ministries are now being strongly promoted by the Universal Church as can be seen in the latest Church Documents. See The Apostolic Letter of Pope Francis (11 January 2021), “*Spiritus Domini*” which opens up ministries of ‘Lector’ and ‘Acolyte’ to *laywomen and men*, and his Apostolic Letter (*Motu Proprio*), “*Antiquum Ministerium*” (on the Ministry of Catechist – 10 May 2021) establishing ‘the *lay ministry of Catechist*’ is significant.

This requires serious consideration and follow-up in the context of the ‘new ministry of the lay Catechist,’ and of extending the ministries of ‘Lector’ and ‘Acolyte’ to the Laity. First of all, the laity will understand that the Church is the sign and sacrament of salvation, and that their ministry is a gift/call from God, and not a claim to take over the functions of the clergy. The Laity sanctify themselves in the exercise of their responsibilities. Further, it will avoid confusing the roles of the laity and the clergy. ‘Clericalization’ of the laity³ is as bad as ‘clericalism’ and ‘secularization’ of the clergy and religious.

Conclusion

What the Holy Father expects from this Synod is, not to produce documents, but to place the entire Church in a condition to live an authentic synodal experience, which matters the most: walking together, stimulating trust, building bridges, healing wounds, enlightening minds and strengthening our hands for our common mission. We are re-learning synodality, and one of the main challenges is that, with synodality, we learn by doing. It’s an easy concept to put into words, but not to put into practice.

The establishment of synodal structures and institutions does not in itself solve problems. A conversion process, to the common good of the community and changes that go deeper in terms of mindset/“habit of mind,” with corresponding values, attitudes and practices will be necessary. A paradigm shift from the old authority-based governance (authoritarianism) to one of “pastoral power,” which includes consultation, exchange, listening, and even dissent to arrive at decisions through discernment will be necessary. Then, ‘Synodality will become a threshold for the Church to cross for its life and its mission in the new millennium.’

The synodal process has created a “great love and passion for the Church.” Let us hope and pray that this passion and love be translated into reality which will lead to the emergence of the Church as a communion of communities, listening to and creating space for the Spirit and to one another, and forging ahead with a sense common mission to the world. Such a Church might come to be seen as the lasting legacy of Pope Francis’ Petrine ministry.

³Pope Francis warns against ‘clericalization of the laity saying that their aspiration should not be to form part of the “Sanhedrin” that gathers around the parish priest, but to be part of the ‘school of holiness and to be an evangelizer.’

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